

Fidelity distribution KDE

(a) Transmitted only (n=18)
Hartigan dip $p = 0.046$; KDE-gap = 0.000

(b) With failures included (n=26)
Hartigan dip $p < 0.0001$; KDE-gap = 0.669
(structural $y=0$ cluster; reported for transparency)

